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Technical Report on Task A of EFSA's priority pest mandate (M-2022-00070)

Host plants of Union Quarantine Pests

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Abstract

In 2022, EFSA was mandated by the European Commission (EC) to support the EC's Joint Research Centre (JRC) of Sevilla in the prioritisation of the Union Quarantine Pests (UQPs). This mandate is articulated in three different tasks to provide data that are scientifically sound on pest ecology (hosts and spread) and impact on hosts. Task A aimed to provide a list of the host plants of the UQPs. Task B is dedicated to support the JRC in shortlisting the UQPs considering their spread and impact. Task C is targeted at providing a set of parameters for the Impact Indicator for Priority Pests (I2P2). I2P2, developed and run by the JRC will finally provide EC and Member States with a reasoned ranking of all candidate priority pests.

In this report, EFSA describes the approach and methodology developed under Task A and the type of data provided to JRC.

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1 Introduction

The European Commission requested EFSA to provide technical assistance in the field of plant health for supporting the listing of the Union Quarantine pests (UQPs) qualifying as priority pests under Regulation (EU) 2016/2031¹. This regulation defines the priority pests as the plant pests that could cause the most severe potential economic, environmental or social impact for the Union territory. The priority pests are subject to special provisions such as annual surveys and contingency plans. The UQP which qualify as priority pests are listed in the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/1702.

For UQP to be included in the list of priority pests of the EU, they should fulfil the following conditions:

- i) they are not known to be present in the Union territory or are known to be present either in a limited part of that territory or for scarce, irregular, isolated and infrequent presences in it;
- ii) their potential economic, environmental or social impact is the most severe in respect of the Union territory.

In 2019, for the establishment of this list, EFSA provided scientific and technical support to the Commission to allow its Directorate-General Joint Research Centre (DG JRC) to calculate the indicators included in the Impact Indicator on Priority Pests (I2P2) (EFSA, 2019²).

In view of a potential revision of Regulation (EU) 2019/1702, in March 2022, EFSA received a mandate (M-2022-0070) from the European Commission (DG SANTE) for providing data to support the JRC in the ranking of the UQPs. This mandate is articulated in three different tasks:

Task A aims to provide a list of the host plants of the UQPs.

Task B is dedicated to support the JRC providing data they required for ranking the UQPs in view of shortlisting less than 60 UQPs (so called 'candidate priority pests') considering their spread and impact.

Task C is targeted at providing, for each of these (<60) candidate priority pests, an estimation of a set of parameters through fully fledged expert knowledge elicitations.

These will be the input data for running the JRC model on the Impact Indicator for Priority Pests (I2P2) that will finally provide a reasoned ranking of all candidate priority pests.

Finally, based on these results, the European Commission and Member States will be able to update the current list of 20 priority pests in force under Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/1702³.

Compared to the methodology developed and applied in 2019, some adjustments were performed in the course of this mandate.

The UQPs include species from all taxonomic groups (i.e. bacteria, phytoplasmas, fungi, insects and mites, nematodes, viruses and viroids).

This document and accompanying Excel file are prepared by EFSA as requested for this TASK A of the mandate (M-2022-00070) i.e. EFSA is requested to provide in November 2022, scientific

and technical support to DG JRC for the analysis of all UQPs (provision of hosts for all UQPs, based on the EPPO Global Database, if information is available, or other sources).

2 Methodology

EFSA discussed in several meetings with the European Commission and the JRC to agree on the methodological approach for addressing Tasks A and B. In particular, the definition of host plants was discussed, and several proposals for the pre-selection of pests were discussed.

2.1 Definition of host plant

The term “host plants” is applied with different meanings by internationally applied frameworks. Three relevant examples are provided below.

- E.g.1 ISPM5¹

Host pest list: A list of pests that infest a plant species, globally or in an area [CEPM, 1996; revised CEPM, 1999]

Host range: Species capable, under natural conditions, of sustaining a specific pest or other organism [FAO, 1990; revised ISPM 3, 2005]

- E.g.2 EPPO² (General user guide of the EPPO Global Database)

The pest/host plant combinations are classed in seven categories. In particular:

Major host: a host plant which is important for the pest, or on that plant the pest is considered to be important. This category is assigned by the EPPO Secretariat, resulting from a qualitative judgement, and using available information (e.g. the plant is frequently considered in the literature as an important host, significant damage is observed). The fact that the host status has been demonstrated (full cycle, Koch’s postulate completed) or that the plant is a preferred host (choice studies) will be indicated together with the bibliographic references whenever data is available.

Host: the plant is listed as a host in the literature. The fact that it is a confirmed host, or a preferred host will be indicated together with the bibliographic references whenever data is available. Similarly if the plant is only used by certain pest stages (adult/larval feeding) or has been shown to be a poor host (e.g. as used in nematology) this could also be indicated if known.

- E.g.3 USDA NAL Agricultural Thesaurus³

¹ <https://www.ippc.int/fr/publications/622/> consulted on 08/12/2023

² https://qd.eppo.int/media/files/general_user-guide.pdf consulted on 08/12/2023

³ <https://agclass.nal.usda.gov/vocabularies/nalt/concept?uri=https://lod.nal.usda.gov/nalt/40972#:~:text=Definition%3A,life%20cycle%20of%20another%20organism> consulted on 08/12/2023

Host plants: Plants which provide shelter, habitat, breeding sites or serve as a food source as part of the life cycle of another organism.

Finally, in biological terms, a "host plant" is typically the plant on which an organism lives and grows. In none of the biological definitions of host plant a clear association is mentioned with the impact the pest could cause on the host plant except for the EPPO Major host without providing further information.

2.2 Regulated taxonomic entities

2.2.1 Polyphagous pests

The ranking of the polyphagous pests based on the host range was discussed. The pests with the broadest host range, in particular when it includes hosts of economic importance, will have higher chances to be retained for further analyses, independently from the potential impact they could cause in the EU. This bias in the ranking increases further in case of taxonomical entities regulated at family or genus level (macrogroups of pests).

2.2.2 Pests absent from the EU

The uncertainties linked to the knowledge of the host range were highlighted for pests absent from the EU, in particular, the pests for which the ecology in a new geographical area is difficult to predict.

2.3 Proposals for inclusion in the shortlisting process

Several EFSA proposals were discussed in view of improving the shortlisting process:

2.3.1 MS consultation

EFSA proposed to consult the MSs for gathering their concerns and thoughts about the pests that would deserve further analysis in Task C. EFSA proposed to support a guided consultation possibly using an expert knowledge elicitation approach.

However, the use of this approach was not considered appropriate by the European Commission for the purpose of pest prioritisation indicating that the basis of the shortlisting should be the ecology of the pest (spread and impact) combined with the economic and environmental impact caused by the pests.

2.3.2 PeMo scoring

EFSA proposed to use the PeMo approach for the screening of all the UQPs for aiding the shortlisting process. PeMo scoring (EFSA et al., 2022) is routinely applied by EFSA on new emerging pests (not regulated) for understanding their relevance. The approach consists of applying a pest index obtained from scoring 15 criteria related to the pest ecology and biology (including spread and impact) and management, included uncertainties and knowledge gaps. This index is compared to a reference list of pests to understand whether the species under assessment represents a potential threat to the EU. This resource intensive approach could have been followed if agreed at the beginning of the mandate for covering all regulated UQPs.

The use of this approach was not considered appropriate by the European Commission for the purpose of pest prioritisation due to the fact that the PeMo methodology was developed for a different purpose.

2.3.3 Horizon scanning, EU interceptions and outbreaks

EFSA proposed to use the results of the Horizon scanning activity to retain the pest species for which there is a major concern, focussing on the number of items retained from media and scientific literature, during the horizon scanning activity and selection of articles for inclusion in the monthly newsletter. For also addressing the potential risk of entry and establishment of the pests in the EU, information from interceptions at EU borders and reported outbreaks of UQP in the EU can be retrieved. The relevance of the pest (number of items retained) combined with the reported interceptions and outbreaks could be integrated with the host range of the pests.

However, the use of this approach was not considered appropriate by the European Commission for the purpose of pest prioritisation.

2.4 Agreed approach

Finally, it was agreed to select the pests based on their spread capacity and their economic and environmental impact on host plants. This information and data provided by EFSA should support the JRC to shortlist the most relevant pests for further assessments in Task C.

2.5 Literature search

The main objective of Task A is to provide for all the UQPs, the host plants that have been identified in the literature. The data extraction was conducted between September and October 2022.

2.5.1 From regulated taxonomic entities to pest species

The pests for which the work was performed are the single pest species that are, or are included in, the regulated taxonomic entities of Annex II of the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/2072⁴.

2.5.2 Excluded pest species

2.5.2.1 Pest vectors

It was agreed with DG SANTE and JRC, the data extraction was not conducted for pests that are regulated only as a result of their vectoring capacity, specifically:

Bemisia tabaci (non-European populations)

Cicadomorpha, known to be vectors of *Xylella fastidiosa*

Diaphorina citri

Myndus crudus

Pityophthorus juglandis

Trioza erytreae

2.5.2.2 Pest regulated above species level

In case of macrogroups (i.e., taxa given at family or genus level) where the individual species names are not provided in the legislation, the outputs of the horizon scanning activity (i.e., items mentioned in published newsletter) were used to identify emerging threats having caused concerns in the last years. The review considered all the newsletters published from the first Media Monitoring Newsletter (March 2017) to the Horizon Scanning Newsletter of October 2022 (corresponding to the last published newsletter at the moment of the exercise). This was applied to

Atropellis: no species identified

Cronartium spp.: 1 species (*C. fusiforme*)

Gymnosporangium spp.: 2 species (*G. clavipes*, *G. yamadae*)

Monochamus spp. (non-European populations): 1 species (*M. alternatus*)

Scolytinae spp. (non-European): 11 species (*Cnestus mutilatus*, *Dendroctonus frontalis*, *D. ponderosae*, *D. rufipennis*, *D. valens*, *Ips calligraphus*, *I. grandicollis*, *Pityophthorus opaculus*, *Polygraphus proximus*, *Scolytus ventralis*, *Xylosandrus compactus*)

Adrama: no species identified

Anastrepha spp.: 3 species (*A. bahiensis*, *A. fraterculus*, *A. grandis*)

Bactrocera spp.: 5 species (*B. carambolae*, *B. facialis*, *B. occipitalis*, *B. passiflorae*, *B. tryoni*)

Ceratitis spp.: 1 species (*C. rosa*)

Dacus spp.: 1 species (*D. ciliatus*)

Eutreta spp.: no species identified

Gymnocarena spp.: no species identified

Procecidochares spp.: no species identified

Rhagoletis spp.: no species identified

Strauzia spp.: no species identified

Zeugodacus spp.: 1 species (*Z. cucurbitae*)

Hirschmanniella spp.: 2 species (*H. mucronate*, *H. oryzae*)

Arceuthobium spp.: no species identified

Begomoviruses: 15 species (*Ageratum yellow vein virus*, *Allamanda leaf mottle distortion virus*, *Clerodendron yellow mosaic virus*, *Cotton leaf curl Gezira virus*, *Cotton leaf curl Multan virus*, *Euphorbia leaf curl virus*, *Euphorbia yellow mosaic virus*, *Papaya leaf curl Guandong virus*, *Papaya leaf curl virus*, *Sida leaf curl virus*, *Squash leaf curl China virus*, *Tomato leaf curl Joydebpur virus*, *Tomato leaf curl Palampur virus*, *Tomato mottle virus*, *Tomato yellow leaf curl Thailand virus*)

Pomacea: 2 species (*P. canaliculata*, *P. maculata*)

2.5.3 Sources of information

For each pest three sources of information were consulted and the host list results from the data extracted in the following sequence:

- I. EPPO Global Database. The pest/host plant combinations are classed in the following seven categories: Major hosts, Hosts, Alternate, Doubtful, Wild/weed, Experimental, Non-host. Hosts belonging to the last two categories were not extracted.
- II. EFSA outputs. Priority was given to Pest categorisations and Pest Survey cards. In absence of those, also other reports and opinions were consulted, e.g., Priority pest reports.
- III. CABI Compendium

The overlaps between the EPPO source and EFSA source were marked, additional species included, and uncertainties highlighted in the content of EFSA opinions indicated in a dedicated column of notes in the Excel file. For each EFSA output the doi is provided for enabling an easy access and check. Finally, the CABI Compendium was consulted, and additional host species not retrieved from the two previously mentioned sources were included.

If no information was found using the EPPO, EFSA or CABI sources, other authoritative documents were considered (e.g., national PRAs, international databases) and the alternative source referenced in the notes.

An exception was made for *Xylella fastidiosa* as EFSA publishes an updated host plant database every 6 months for this pest. Thus, only this source was taken into account for *Xylella fastidiosa*. It is also important to note that no distinction was made among subspecies of the bacterium and that only naturally infected host plant species that were verified with two or more detection methods (including microscopy) were selected for data extraction.

For *Xiphinema americanum sensu stricto* and *Xiphinema bricolense* the host range was too generic for inclusion of plant species in the database (i.e. agricultural, horticultural and forest soils).

2.5.4 Categories of hosts

In order to further help clustering the pests, EFSA provided in the Excel file two columns dedicated to the type of hosts: agricultural, forestry, ornamental/wild. The first column identifying the first most represented category, and second representing the following one.

The decision about the type of host indicated in each column was based on the relative number of species belonging to each category and based on individual judgement. This additional classification was provided with the intention to help clustering pests with the JRC approach proposed during the first mandate: agricultural, forestry, agroforestry pests.

2.6 Additional task

EFSA provided further support to the JRC by identifying the correspondences between the hosts file delivered by EFSA as a result of TASK A and the JRC adopted datasets reflecting EUROSTAT and FAOSTAT crop and commodity categories, and host plants listed in cultural heritage sites.

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The major difficulty of this task was to connect EUROSTAT and FAOSTAT categories with the host plant species and resulted in many unclear and uncertain connections.

3 Conclusion

In 2022, EFSA was mandated by the European Commission (EC) to support the EC's Joint Research Centre (JRC) of Sevilla in the prioritisation of the Union Quarantine Pests (UQPs). This mandate is articulated in three different tasks to provide data that are scientifically sound on pest ecology (hosts and spread), impact on hosts and other risk drivers. Task A aimed to provide a list of the host plants of the UQPs. Task B is dedicated to support the JRC in shortlisting the UQPs considering their spread and impact. Task C is targeted at providing a set of parameters for the Impact Indicator for Priority Pests (I2P2). I2P2, developed and run by the JRC will finally deliver to EC and Member States a reasoned ranking of all candidate priority pests.

In December 2022 the EFSA work on listing the possible hosts of all the UQPs was delivered and resulted in more than 11,500 pest-host combinations. In this report, EFSA describes the approach and methodology developed under Task A and the type of data provided to JRC in a dedicated Excel file (published together with this report).

Following the application to these pest host combinations of the ranking approach developed by the JRC, a preliminary ranking of pests resulting from the estimation of the economic and environmental impact was provided. However, this preliminary screening delivered results that are not supported by the current general knowledge and existing evidence on the top ranked pest species. Two main reasons could explain this:

- i) For each pest-host combination, it is assumed that the impact corresponds to a total loss in production. However, the impact that a pest can cause on a given host can vary from very minor to extremely high (with the complete destruction of the crop) depending on a number of aspects connected to pest and host biology, ecoclimatic conditions, type of product.
- ii) Scientific names of the plant species are required to match with the nomenclature and commercial categories used in EUROSTAT and FAOSTAT (e.g., production and price). However, EFSA pest-host combinations are provided at plant species level as obtained from the scientific evidence (publications and databases) and this matching with commercial categories applied in the above mentioned statistical databases is not always possible due to: a) different level of aggregation, b) translation of common names applied in stats to specific taxonomic identities, c) absence of many plant species, also of economic relevance, such as ornamental species.

Following these preliminary results from Task A, in Task B EFSA was tasked to further support the JRC integrating spread and impact data to retain a shortlist that will allow to perform a more accurate analysis of the economic and environmental impacts.

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